

DAMAGE MECHANICS MODEL FOR OFF-AXIS FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITES AT ROOM AND HIGH TEMPERATURES

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SUMMARY: Tension-tension fatigue tests were performed for unidirectional T800H/Epoxy at room temperature (RT) and 100°C, respectively, using seven kinds of plain coupon specimens with different fiber orientation angles. The characteristic nature of the fiber-matrix interface controlled off-axis fatigue failure was similar at RT and 100°C. Irrespective of off-axis angle, almost linear S-N relationships were obtained in the whole range of fatigue testing up to 10^6 cycles. Normalizing the maximum fatigue stress with respect to the static tensile strength at test temperature, the off-axis fatigue data eventually fell on a single S-N relationship. A non-dimensional effective stress defined on the basis of the classical static failure theory succeeded in coping with the directional nature of the off-axis fatigue behavior in a unified manner. By using the non-dimensional effective stress in the continuum damage mechanics approach, a general failure model was developed to describe the observed off-axis S-N relationships.

KEYWORDS: Off-Axis Fatigue, Temperature Dependence, Fatigue Damage, S-N Curve, Non-Dimensional Effective Stress, Damage Mechanics, Carbon Fiber, Epoxy Resin

INTRODUCTION

For unidirectional composites consisting of high stiffness/strength fiber and brittle polymer matrix, the longitudinal fatigue failure occurs usually with some parallel splittings extending along fibers into the end tab regions and pullouts of strips fractured transversely in either of the end tab regions. In the case of the off-axis fatigue loading, on the other hand, the ultimate failure takes place in a single weakest cross section along the reinforcing fibers, regardless of off-axis angle. Therefore, it is obvious that the off-axis fatigue failure of unidirectional composites is influenced by the mechanical properties of matrix and fiber-matrix interface/interphase [1]. The ductility and strength of polymer matrix and fiber-matrix interface/interphase markedly change with temperature and moisture content. The variations in these mechanical properties result in significant effects on the inelastic deformation and damage of unidirectional laminae under off-axis fatigue loading conditions. For example, an increase in the resin ductility suppresses the extension of local damage developing in the matrix and interphase, and it enhances the nonlinear shear deformation in the fiber-matrix

interface region. A decrease in the strength of matrix or interphase lowers the off-axis strength. These imply that the changes in ductility and strength of the matrix and in adhesive strength of the fiber-matrix interfaces due to different environmental (thermal and hygroscopic) conditions have marked effects on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites. Therefore, it is important to elucidate effects of the changes in ductility and strength of the matrix and fiber-matrix interface/interphase on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional laminae and to include them in the fatigue design analysis for composites.

The present study aims to elucidate the effects of test temperature on the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional continuous carbon fiber composite T800/Epoxy and to develop a fatigue failure model based on the continuum damage mechanics. For these purposes, tension-tension fatigue tests were performed at room temperature (RT) and 100°C, respectively, using plain coupon specimens with different off-axis angles: 0, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, and 90°. From a comparison between the relative fatigue strengths at room and high temperatures, the effects of property changes in the epoxy resin due to temperature on the off-axis fatigue behavior were elucidated. Capabilities of the conventional fatigue strength parameters to systematically describe the off-axis S-N relationships were also examined. To model the fiber-matrix interface controlled off-axis fatigue failure, a non-dimensional multiaxial effective stress was defined on the basis of the classical static failure theory [2]. The non-dimensional effective stress is interpreted as a theoretical strength ratio in the case of off-axis fatigue loading, and as an interfacial effective stress characterizing the fiber-matrix interface controlled off-axis fatigue failure of unidirectional laminae. Finally, by using this non-dimensional effective stress in the continuum damage mechanics approach [3], an attempt was made to develop a macroscopic fatigue failure model for predicting the observed off-axis fatigue behavior. Through numerical simulations, the validity of the proposed model was tested.

MATERIAL AND SPECIMENS

The material for the present study is a unidirectional (UD) composite laminate fabricated using the autoclave method from the prepreg (P2053-17, TORAY) which consists of carbon fiber (TORAYCA T800H, TORAY) and thermosetting epoxy resin (2500EP, the curing temperature of 130°C). The lay-up of the virgin laminate is $[0]_{12}$. From the optical micrograph of the cross-section perpendicular to the fiber direction, it was found that the fiber volume fraction V_f was about 64 %.

Nine kinds of plain coupon specimens with different off-axis angles ($\theta = 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, 60$ and 90°) were cut from 400 mm by 400 mm UD laminate panels. The specimen dimensions are specified as follows: the specimen length $L = 200$ mm; the gauge length $L_G = 100$ mm ; and the thickness $t = 2$ mm, respectively. The specimen width (W) is 10 mm for $\theta = 0^\circ$, and 25 mm for all other off-axis angles.

Fig. 1: Off-axis S-N relationships for unidirectional T800H/Epoxy laminate at RT

Rectangular-shaped aluminum alloy tabs were bonded on both ends of the specimens using epoxy adhesive (ARALDITE); the thickness of the end-tabs is 1.0 mm.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Off-axis static tension and tension-tension fatigue tests for T800H/2500EP were performed using a hydraulic servo testing machine at room temperature (RT, about 23°C) and high temperature (HT, 100°C), respectively. Specimens were clamped by the hydraulic grip fitted on the testing machine. The static tension tests were performed with stroke control at RT and HT, and the cross-head speed was specified to be 1.0 mm/min. The tension-tension fatigue tests were carried out at constant amplitudes under a load control mode. The fatigue load was applied at a constant stress ratio $R = 0.1$ in a sinusoidal waveform with a frequency of 10 Hz. The fatigue tests were terminated at the cut-off cycle of 10^6 .

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Off-Axis Fatigue Behavior at RT

S-N relationships using maximum fatigue stress

The S-N relationships at RT for the off-axis angles $\theta = 10, 15, 30, 45^\circ$ and 90° are presented in **Fig. 1**. The off-axis fatigue strength becomes smaller as the off-axis angle increases. The off-axis S-N relationships are well represented by the straight lines with negative slopes which start from the values of static tensile strength plotted on the vertical axis, although a small disorder is involved in the case $\theta = 30^\circ$ at a low cycle fatigue range. The slopes of the

Fig. 2: Normalized S-N relationships at RT using fatigue elastic strain range $\Delta\sigma/E_x(\theta)$

Fig. 3: Normalized S-N relationships at RT using experimental fatigue strength ratio $\sigma_{max}/\sigma_{B(exp)}$

approximated straight lines tend to become more gradual as the off-axis angle increases. The static strength-dependence in the low cycle regime and the fatigue limit were not clearly observed in these off-axis fatigue tests.

Effects of fatigue strength parameter on S-N relationships

The S-N relationships plotted using a fatigue elastic strain range $\Delta\epsilon^e$ instead of the maximum fatigue stress are presented in Fig. 2 for the fatigue data at RT discussed above. The fatigue elastic strain range was defined as $\Delta\epsilon^e = \Delta\sigma/E_x$, where $\Delta\sigma [= (1-R)\sigma_{max}]$ represents the fatigue stress range and E_x is the Young's modulus in the fatigue loading direction. From Fig. 2, it is found that the fatigue data points separate into two groups associated with the fiber direction ($\theta = 0^\circ$) and the other off-axis directions ($0^\circ < \theta \leq 90^\circ$) and that the data band for the latter

group is very narrow. This result implies that the fatigue failure of unidirectional composites is dominated by different physical mechanisms for these two groups.

Another kind of normalization of the maximum fatigue stress σ_f can be made using the static strength σ_{θ} in place of the Young's modulus E_x . Fig. 3 shows the off-axis S-N relationships plotted using the experimental strength ratio $\sigma_f / \sigma_{\theta}$; σ_{θ} denotes the observed off-axis static tensile strength. From this figure, it is observed that the normalized fatigue data points randomly distribute in a relatively narrow band regardless of off-axis angle. The same tendency has been found by Awerbuch and Hahn [4] in their experimental results for a unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite at RT. The width of the normalized fatigue data band is not negligibly small. However, it is believed as a first approximation that the experimental strength ratio is a useful parameter to cope with the orientation dependence of the off-axis fatigue behavior of unidirectional composites.

Off-Axis Fatigue Behavior at 100°C

S-N relationships using maximum fatigue stress

The off-axis fatigue behavior observed at 100°C for the off-axis angle range $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$ is shown in Fig. 4. The S-N relationships are almost linear for every off-axis angle in the range $N_f < 10^6$, and the fatigue strength becomes lower as the off-axis angle increases. The static strength-dependence and the fatigue limit are not clearly observed in the range of the present fatigue testing up to 10^6 . These characteristics are common to the off-axis fatigue behavior at RT and 100°C.

The effect of temperature can be found in the significant reduction of the absolute fatigue strength (i.e., the level of maximum fatigue stress). Compared between the S-N data at RT and 100°C for each off-axis angle in the range $0^\circ < \theta < 90^\circ$, it is found that the fatigue strength at 100°C falls to one-half to two-thirds of that at RT. This almost corresponds to the decrease in off-axis static strength due to the increase in test temperature. The fatigue strength at 100°C in the fiber direction is almost as high as that at RT, and it cannot be shown in Fig. 4. From these observations, therefore, it is confirmed that the strength reduction of the epoxy resin, fiber-matrix interface or interphase due to high temperature have significant influences on the off-axis fatigue strength of unidirectional composites.

Fig. 4: Off-axis S-N relationships for unidirectional T800H/Epoxy laminate at 100°C

Effects of fatigue strength parameter on S-N relationships

The relationships between the fatigue elastic strain range ($\Delta\varepsilon^e = \Delta\sigma/E_x$) and the logarithm of fatigue lifetime N_f for the high temperature off-axis fatigue were similar to those for the RT off-axis fatigue. This result again indicates that different fatigue failure mechanisms operate for these two groups. The macroscopic fatigue failure morphology observed at 100°C was similar to that at RT. Therefore, the microscopic fatigue failure mechanisms at 100°C which characterize these two groups are also believed to be similar.

Regarding the normalized S-N relationships using the experimental strength ratio $\sigma_{\max}/\sigma_{B(\text{exp})}$ at high temperature, the width of the data band is slightly wider as compared with the similar plots for the RT fatigue. No appreciable effects of the off-axis angle on the fatigue lifetime can be observed in this plot. Accepting the logic used by Awerbuch and Hahn [4], therefore, it may be concluded that the experimental strength ratio becomes a useful parameter to manipulate also the off-axis angle dependence of high-temperature fatigue.

NON-DIMENSIONAL EFFECTIVE STRESS

On the basis of the Tsai-Hill quadratic interaction criterion [1, 2], a non-dimensional scalar quantity σ^* is defined as follows:

$$(1)$$

In a particular case where a tensile stress σ_x is applied to an off-axis plain coupon specimen in the longitudinal (x-axis) direction, the non-dimensional effective stress becomes

$$(2)$$

where θ denotes the off-axis angle. The orientation factor $\Omega(\theta)$ is given by

(3)

where X and Y represent the longitudinal and transverse strengths in either tension or compression and S denotes the shear strength.

The off-axis static tensile failure occurs when the following condition is satisfied:

(4)

The predicted tensile strength $\sigma_{B(\text{pred})}$ in the loading direction is thus expressed as

(5)

The maximum fatigue stress normalized with respect to this theoretical static fracture strength is described as

(6)

Therefore, the maximum non-dimensional effective stress associated with the maximum fatigue stress can be interpreted as a theoretical strength ratio for the off-axis loading on plain coupon specimens.

FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANICS MODEL

Evolution Equation for Fatigue Damage

It is assumed that a state of the fatigue damage of unidirectional composite is described by a single scalar variable ω and its growth is prescribed by the following equation:

(7)

where K , n , and k are material constants. The fatigue strength parameter Φ is specified by either of the following:

(8)

Fig. 5: On- and off-axis S-N relationships predicted using fatigue damage mechanics model (RT)

where σ_{max} is the non-dimensional effective stress range corresponding to the fatigue stress range $\Delta\sigma$.

Fatigue Life Equation

Imposing an initial condition that $\omega = 0$ when $N = 0$, Eqn 7 can be integrated to obtain the analytic expression of the fatigue damage. Assuming that a final fracture occurs when ω has reached unity, we can derive the following expression of the fatigue lifetime:

$$(9)$$

Setting $\Phi =$ and $N_f = 1$ when $= 1$, we find $(k+1)K = 1$. Then, the fatigue lifetime can be represented as

$$(10)$$

Application to Off-Axis Fatigue

In Eqn 10, the material constant to be determined is the only exponent n , except for the static strengths X , Y and S . The value of $-1/n$ is identified as the slope of the straight line which starts from the point $(\log N_f, \log) = (1, 1)$ and approximates to the normalized S-N

Fig. 6: On- and off-axis S-N relationships predicted by using fatigue damage mechanics model (100°C)

relationships between $\log \sigma_{max}$ and $\log N_f$. The exponents evaluated for the fatigue data at room and high temperatures are $n = 22.07$ and $n = 22.05$, respectively. The difference between these exponents is very small. Thus, the normalized master S-N relationship is independent of test temperature.

Figs. 5 and 6 show the comparisons between the theoretical and experimental S-N relationships for the off-axis fatigue at RT and 100°C, respectively. It is observed that the fatigue damage mechanics model can describe the characteristic nature of the off-axis fatigue behavior at these temperatures.

CONCLUSIONS

Off-axis tensile fatigue behavior of unidirectional T800H/Epoxy composite was examined at room (RT) and high (100°C) temperatures under constant amplitude condition, and the influence of the temperature-dependence of the strengths of matrix and fiber-matrix interface/interphase was elucidated. A particular emphasis was placed on the identification of the mechanical parameter to describe the directional nature of the off-axis fatigue strength. It was demonstrated that a non-dimensional effective stress defined using the classical failure criterion might be used as an alternative strength parameter for a systematic description of the fatigue behavior of unidirectional composite laminae. An attempt was also made to develop a damage mechanics model for the off-axis fatigue behavior, and it was checked on the basis of the experimental results.

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